

HUMAN-CENTRIC AI-ENABLED EXTENDED REALITY APPLICATIONS FOR THE
INDUSTRY 5.0 ERA

D7.1 – DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNITY BUILDING
PLAN V1

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CONTRIBUTING PARTNERS

Partner Acronym	Role	Name Surname
INNOV-ACTS (INNOV)	Lead Beneficiary & Editor	Elina Vasiliki Papadopoulou, Evanthia Vorilla, John Soldatos,
ALL Partners	Contributors	

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Definition
AAR	All About Remote
ACM	Association for Computing Machinery
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIDA	Attention Interest Desire Action
AIOTI	Alliance for IoT Innovation
AITI	Associazione Industrie Ticinesi
AL	Active Learning
APMS	Advances in Production Management Systems
AR	Augmented Reality
AVR	Augmented and Virtual Reality
AWE	Augmented World Expo
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CEN/ CENELEC	European Committee for Standardization /European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
CES	Consumer Electronics Show
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DAIRO	Data Artificial Intelligence and Robotics
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DoA	Description of Action
DTC	Digital Twin Consortium
DTs	Digital Twins
EBDVF	European Big Data Value Forum
EIRA	European Interoperability Reference Architecture
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
EFTA	Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation
ERCIM	European Research Consortium for Informatics and Mathematics
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FSTP	Financial Support for Third Parties
F2F	Face to Face
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GenAI	Generative Artificial Intelligence
GICAI	Global Insight Conference on Artificial Intelligence
ICHVR	International Conference on Haptics and Virtual Reality
IEEE	Institute of Electric and Electronic Engineers
IFIP	International Federation of Information Processing
IIRA	Industrial Internet Reference Architecture
INCITS	International Committee for Information Technology Standards
INDIN	IEEE International Conference on Industrial Informatics
ISMAR	International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality
ISO	International Organization for Standardization

IVRAM	Industrial Value Chain Reference Architecture
I5.0	Industry 5.0
KGA	Knowledge Graph Alliance
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LASFA	LAsim Smart Factory
MCNA	Multimedia Computing, Networking and Applications
MR	Mixed Reality
OA	Open Access
OMG	Object Management Group
ONNX	Open Neural Network Exchange
OREPP	Open Research Europe Publishing Platform
OSS	Open Source Software
PID	Persistent Identifier
PMML	Predictive Model Markup Language
QA	Quality Assurance
RAMI	Reference Architectural Model Industrie 4.0
ROI	Return on Investment
R&D	Research and Development
SDOs	Standards Development Organizations
SITAM	Stuttgart IT-Architecture for Manufacturing
SSF	Switzerland Innovation Park Biel/Bienne AG
TOGAF	The Open Group Architectural Framework
UC	Use Case
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
TEF	Testing and Experimentation Facilities
VR	Virtual Reality
VRIF	Virtual Reality Industry Forum
VRST	Virtual Reality Software and Technology
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence
XR	Extended Reality

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main goal of the XR5.0 project is to develop, demonstrate, and validate an innovative Person-Centric AI-based paradigm for industrial XR applications for the Industry 5.0 era. In this direction, the project is developing innovative "XR-made-in-Europe" technologies that foster a seamless integration of industrial XR applications with human-centric manufacturing technologies, including trustworthy AI technologies. One of the main objectives of the project is to develop a vibrant ecosystem (XR5.0-Ecosystem) of interested and engaged stakeholders around the project's results, including a community of manufacturers, providers of industrial automation solutions, Industry 5.0 and AI researchers, as well as policymakers and Standards Development Organizations (SDOs). This community will be one of the main vehicles for the exploitation, sustainability, and wider use of the project's results beyond the end of the project.

To develop the XR5.0-Ecosystem and community around the project's results, XR5.0 is already undertaking a series of dissemination, communication, and community building activities as part of an ambitious dissemination and communication plan. The main principles and targets (including Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)) of this plan are documented in the project's DoA (Description of Action) document that is part of the XR5.0 Grant Agreement i.e., contract with the European Commission. Driven by these principles and KPIs targets, the present deliverable presents a quite extensive dissemination and communication plan, including concrete dissemination and communication activities as well as more details about dissemination channels and the XR5.0 partners that will be involved in the implementation of the activities of the plan. Along with the dissemination and communication plan of the project, the present deliverables reports a set of early dissemination and communication activities that have been completed and accomplished by the project partners during the first four months of the project's lifetime. These accomplishments concern the establishment of the project's presence in social media, as well as a first set of publications.

The detailed plan of the project's dissemination and communication activities presents many different types of activities that will be carried out by the project, including scientific publications, workshops, collaboration with other projects, participation in exhibitions, organization of webinars, dissemination posts through social media channels and more. Emphasis is also paid in listing pre-standardization activities and activities that aim at providing XR5.0 contributions to industrial associations and project clusters. The latter represent special and important tasks of the project's workplan, which underlines their prominent role in the project's dissemination and communication activities.

In terms of the timing of the plan activities, the present deliverable provides details for activities planned for up to the first half of the project's lifetime (i.e., M18 / June 2025). Moreover, dissemination activities till the end of the project are outlined. However, details about the dissemination activities that will take place during the second part of the project will be provided and reported in coming WP7 deliverables (i.e., D7.2), which will be delivered closer to this period. Furthermore, the activities planned as part of this deliverable are subject to refinement and fine-tuning as needed to ensure the effectiveness of the XR5.0 dissemination plan and its alignment with the project's evolving needs. Overall, the present deliverable is part of the project's iterative methodology to dissemination planning and execution, which foresees planning and execution of activities, as well as refinement of the plans in-line with the measured effectiveness of the executed activities and with new dissemination requirements arising from the project's activities.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Scope and Purpose

One of the main objectives of the XR5.0 project is to develop a vibrant ecosystem of interested and committed stakeholders around the project's results. To this end, the project will attempt to raise awareness about the project's outcomes to a rich set of relevant stakeholders, including manufacturers, industrial organizations, integrators of Industry 5.0 solutions, AI experts, Industry 5.0 / XR and AI researchers, SDOs, policy makers, regulators and more. Accordingly, it will attempt to convince some of these parties to register with the project's ecosystem platforms and technology platform towards engaging with the project's outcomes. Successfully engaged stakeholders will be then treated as potential customers and potential collaborators towards achieving the exploitation, sustainability, and wider use of the project's results after the end of the project.

The above-listed ecosystem building and community building activities hinge on the implementation of well-structured and ambitious dissemination and communication plan towards the above-listed stakeholder groups. The concept and main principles of such a plan have already been described in the project's DoA. Nevertheless, as this plan stems from the XR5.0 proposal, some of the envisaged activities are not presented in sufficient detail. The purpose of the present deliverable is to provide a detailed plan for the XR5.0 dissemination and communication activities, including information about the project's liaisons and contributions to SDOs, industrial associations, and project clusters. The plan is fairly detailed in terms of the activities to be carried out during the first 18 months of the project i.e., up to June 2025. The activities to be carried out after June 2025 will be detailed in follow up WP7 deliverables of the project starting from D7.2 i.e. the first detailed report of the project on dissemination and communication activities.

The deliverable also includes a list of accomplished dissemination and communication activities, including early publications and the establishment of the project's brand image and presence in social media. The rationale behind reporting these activities lies in that the present deliverable is produced/delivered four months after the start of the project, which means that a set of activities have already been implemented. In terms of the type of activities that are reported and planned, the deliverable targets a quite rich and comprehensive list, including:

- An overview of the branded dissemination and communication materials that have been created during the first four months of the project.
- The communication channels that have been created, including the website and the social media channels of the project.
- Dissemination activities, such as workshops, conferences, webinars, exhibitions, demonstrations, and training events.
- Joint activities and collaboration with related projects.
- Activities concerning collaboration and liaisons with SDOs and industrial organizations.
- The establishment and use of tools for monitoring and fine-tuning the dissemination plans, such as a stakeholders' database, communication KPIs and tools for content structuring and tracking.

The reported plans are subject to refinement and fine-tuning considering the project's evolving needs, as well as stakeholders' feedback regarding the activities and metrics regarding the performance of the activities. This is fully in-line with the project's agile and iterative methodology.

1.2 Methodology

The overarching goal of the project's dissemination and communication strategy is to build a vibrant and strong ecosystem around the project's results, including a community of interested stakeholders. The latter will be the project's candidate customers and collaborators in the XR5.0 efforts to sustain and exploit the project's outcomes in ways that generate significant impact at the European level. Thus, the project's dissemination actions must aim not only to create awareness about the project's results, but also to create a strong interest and desire for stakeholders to engage with the project's results. To this end, the project's methodology adopts principles of the popular AIDA (Attention Interest Desire Action) marketing

methodology, which aims at nudging targeted groups (“persona”) in implementing some call/prompt for action. In the case of XR5.0, dissemination actions will aim at raising awareness about the project and its outcomes, generating interest and desire to engage with the project’s results, and ultimately engaging with the project’s technologies and the use cases. The latter engagement will be targeted at various:

- Levels, including: (i) User level for end-users of XR5.0 technologies and use cases and (ii) Technology level for technology providers/integrators that may wish to adopt and use the project’s scientific and technological outcomes;
- Geographical Scopes, including (i) local/regional scope such as the ecosystems of the use cases and (ii) national/EU scope for engaging with wider ecosystems such as national and EU level industrial associations.

Figure 1: Phased and Iterative Dissemination Methodology of the project.

The variant of the project’s AIDA methodology is structured in three phases each one spanning of the three years of the project’s lifetime (Figure 1):

- **P1 - Awareness Raising (M1-M12):** This phase focuses on raising awareness about the project and its goals to relevant communities and stakeholders. To this end, overview information about the project will be disseminated along with early results. It is also a phase where the main dissemination channels and liaisons of the project are established and substantiated.
- **P2 - Interest and Desire Generation (M13-M24):** The dissemination activities of this phase will aim at generative interest for stakeholders to engage with the project, through presenting technological achievements and use cases with industrial value and potential Return on Investment (ROI).
- **P3 - Ecosystem Engagement (M25-M36):** In this last phase, the dissemination and communication activities will primarily target the actual engagement of stakeholders with the project’s results based on the dissemination of CTA (Call for Action) and the provision of relevant incentives (e.g., access to premium content and demonstrators).

The above listed phases have different, yet complementary themes and centers of gravity regarding the goals of the dissemination activities. However, their goals can also be targeted and accomplished in virtually any phase i.e., it will be possible to achieve engagement of stakeholders with the project’s results even at the early stages of the project in P1. Moreover, the dissemination planning for every phase will clearly adopt

an agile and iterative approach with provisions for adaptation to dynamically changing contexts and the evolving project requirements.

1.3 Deliverable Structure

The remainder of the deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Section 2** following this introductory section, provides information about the logo and the branding elements of the XR5.0 project.
- **Section 3** describes the digital communication channels of the project, which have been already established and used for day-to-day dissemination and communication activities.
- **Section 4** presents the content strategy of the project, including information about relevant KPIs. It also presents the project's tools for tracking progress towards the content-based dissemination target of the project (e.g., blog/content trackers).
- **Section 5** presents a detailed plan for different types of dissemination and communication activities for the XR5.0 results, including for example planning of publications, planning of participation to trade fairs, as well as planning of various webinars and training sessions.
- **Section 6** provides information about the planning of the project's contributions to industrial associations, project clusters and SDOs.
- **Section 7** is the final and concluding section of the deliverable. This section provides an outlook for the evolution of the planning of the dissemination activities and its adaptation to the dynamically changing context of the project.

2. XR5.0 BRAND IDENTIFY

2.1 XR5.0 Logo

The logo creation of the project is the key element in its communication. The XR5.0 logo provides a visual depiction of the project and helps to establish the brand's identity. To make the project name immediately recognizable to everybody, XR5.0 incorporates it within the logo in full, using distinct colors. The thought for the creation of the brand was to create a wordmark, where the logo and the icon merge and create a unique and modern logotype. This way, the typography represents not only the name of the project but also the virtual world through the virtual reality glasses. (Figure 2).

Figure 2 - XR5.0 Official Logo.

In the construction of this wordmark, the space was also taken into consideration, which allows the logo to be used with other logos and still stand out.

The color versions show the many combinations that the logo allows and the correct use of each option (Figure 3).

Figure 3 - Size & Versions of the XR5.0 logo.

During the initial two months of the project, five distinct visuals of the logo were developed in collaboration with creative experts, as illustrated in the accompanying Figure 4.

Figure 4 - Logo Selection.

A specialized poll was conducted to assess the reception of five new logo visuals alongside the logo crafted for the proposal (see Figure 5). Following comprehensive deliberation, the logo featured during the proposal phase emerged as the preferred choice among the majority of partners.

Figure 5 - Logo's Poll Process.

2.2 XR5.0 Branding Materials

Creating a specific stand out from similar projects is crucial, for that reason, there is a specific brand material that XR5.0 uses. At first, the color palette of the project’s visuals is similar to the purple tones of the logo’s colors. Both the look and feel of the website (see Figure 6) and the visuals on social media (see Figure 7) are based on the specific color palette.

Figure 6 - Website look and feel.

Figure 7 - Social Media Layout.

2.3 Templates

Part of the establishment of the project’s brand identity involves the creation of templates for the project’s documents and presentation.

The following elements are part of the document template set:

- Figure 8, Deliverable Template;
- Figure 9, Presentation Template

**HUMAN-CENTRIC AI-ENABLED EXTENDED REALITY APPLICATIONS FOR THE
INDUSTRY 5.0 ERA**

DX.Y – TITLE OF THE DELIVERABLE

Lead Beneficiary	Partner Acronym
Work Package Ref.	WPX – Reference Work package Name
Task Ref.	TX.Z – Reference Task Name
Deliverable Title	DX.Y – Title of the Deliverable
Due Date	yyyy-mm-dd
Delivered Date	yyyy-mm-dd
Revision Number	M.N.
Dissemination Level	Public (PU) or Confidential (CO)
Type	Report (R) or Other (ORDP) or ETHICS
Document Status	Draft or Release
Review Status	Internally Reviewed and/or Quality Assurance Reviewed
Document Acceptance	WP Leader Accepted and/or Coordinator Accepted
EC Project Officer	Ms. Tunde LEVY

Figure 8 - Deliverable Template.

Figure 9 - Presentation Template.

3. COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

3.1 Website

The initial channel to begin communication with the XR5.0 was to develop a functional website (<https://xr50.eu/>) to present and communicate the important pillars of the project. The development of the website started at the beginning of the project. Since the third month of the project, the site has been completed with all the important content. Figure 10 below displays the homepage's banner and the menu that has been added. During the development of the project, the menu will be enhanced with other necessary categories such as "XR5.0 synergies."

Figure 10 - Homepage banner.

Figure 11 below displays the sitemap of the XR5.0 webpage. The site includes six main categories that host the initial content of the website:

- **About:** Describes the project and points out all the significant parts of it, with a subcategory that includes the Synergies of the project.
- **Consortium:** Displays the logos of all the partners. The image is linkable, and it drives users to each partner's website.
- **Pilots:** The six pilots of the project (Rapid Human-Centric AI-Enabled Product Design, Human Centred Remote Maintenance and Asset Management, Operator 5.0 Training for Smart Water Pipes based on XR Streaming, Worker Centric Aircraft Maintenance Training, Increased Effectiveness and Safety of Product Assembly and Repair Processes, Human Centric Guidance and Troubleshooting for Customer Service) are presented in detail.
- **Resources:** There are five subcategories in this section:
 - **Publications:** This section will include all the publications of the project, including access to Green or Gold Open Access Publications.
 - **Deliverables:** This section will include all the public deliverables of the project.
 - **Newsletters:** The newsletters of the project will be also published in this section.
 - **Videos:** All the videos that are uploaded on YouTube will be also displayed in this section.
 - **Communication kit:** The communication kit includes the logo files. The main banner and the flyer will be also added in this section.
- **Contact:** The contact section provides a contact form to provide visitors with the opportunity to get in touch with the project through the project coordinator.
- **News Hub:** This section includes three subcategories:
 - **What's New:** This category provides all the new announcements and information about the project.

- **Events:** Information about every event/ workshop/ webinar where XR5.0 will participate or organise will be published in this section.
- **Blog:** Partners will conduct specific blog posts that will be presented in this section.

Figure 11 - Sitemap of the XR5.0 webpage.

3.2 Social Media

To enhance the dissemination and communication activities four channels have been created. Each channel has a tailor-made strategy to achieve its goals.

3.2.1 LinkedIn

The LinkedIn account for the XR5.0 Project was established at the onset of M1 with the primary objective of promoting and showcasing the results achieved by XR5.0. It serves as a platform to raise awareness among the target audience, generating interest, and attracting participants to the project's events. Additionally, the LinkedIn account aims to foster a dynamic and thriving community around XR5.0, facilitating knowledge exchange and creating a vibrant ecosystem that drives innovation and supports the advancement of the XR industry.

As Figure 12 displays the LinkedIn page of the project has 153 followers (April 20th, 2024). The initial monthly strategy of the first year includes a minimum of 2 posts each month, yet a much higher posting frequency will be implemented in practice.

Figure 12 - LinkedIn page of the project.

The main content of the LinkedIn page includes posts that announce an event/ conference, significant achievements of partners, blog posts of the consortium, posts from project synergies, and relevant reposts.

Furthermore, relevant hashtags have been created to enhance the organic content of the LinkedIn page:

#XR50project #euproject #ai #extendedreality #europeanprojects #horizoneu

Figure 13 – Sample XR5.0 LinkedIn posts.

Figure 14 - LinkedIn repost.

3.2.2 X

The X account of XR5.0 has also been created at the very beginning of the project. The primary focus of the XR5.0 project's X account has been to effectively promote and exhibit the remarkable outcomes accomplished by the XR5.0 initiative. By serving as a strategic platform, it effectively raises awareness within the target audience, generating considerable interest and successfully attracting participants to the project's informative events. Moreover, an integral objective of the X account is to cultivate a dynamic and prosperous community centered around XR5.0.

Similar projects such as @XR4ED_EU, @OpenVerse_EU, @HumAIne_project, @xr2learn_eu, and other accounts have already been followed to enhance the community that XR5.0 will create.

As Figure 15 displays at this moment X account of the XR5.0 project **has 29 followers, and it is following 56 relevant accounts.**

Figure 15 - X Account.

There is a specific content strategy for the X account for the first year of the project that entails regularly uploading a minimum of two posts per month on the account. To further augment the effectiveness of this strategy, approximately eight reposts of similar projects will be included each month. By adhering to this comprehensive content plan, the X account aims to ensure a consistent and engaging presence on the platform, fostering valuable interactions and fostering a sense of collaboration within the community.

Figure 16 - X post.

Figure 17 - X reposts.

3.2.3 Facebook

As Facebook is one of the largest social media platforms globally, the XR5.0 also has a presence. Creating the XR5.0 Facebook provides the opportunity to reach a wide audience, including stakeholders, policymakers, researchers, potential collaborators, and the general public across Europe and beyond.

At this moment Figure 18 depicts the XR5.0 Facebook page. Much as XR5.0 acknowledges the size and potential of Facebook, the project considers LinkedIn as its primary social media/network channel, as it is a more targeted and focused channel towards the primary XR5.0 audience persona(s).

Figure 18 - Facebook Account.

3.2.4 YouTube

A YouTube channel has been created for the XR5.0 project. This channel can play a crucial role in enhancing the visibility, engagement, and impact of the XR5.0 project by providing a platform for communication, collaboration, and multimedia content dissemination. More than 10 videos should be created by the end of the project. Different categories of videos will enhance the content of the XR5.0 YouTube channel e.g. promo videos, Use case videos, videos of webinars/ workshops, and tool tutorials. As illustrated in Figure 19 the YouTube channel of the project has been established.

Figure 19 - YouTube Account.

3.3 Newsletter

The communication strategy of the XR5.0 project includes the development of newsletters. According to KPIs the first year of the project two or more newsletters should be sent to the project’s newsletter recipient’s list. The newsletters refer to a specific target audience which includes partners, consortium members, third parties, and other interested users. To create successful Newsletter campaigns, there is a need to use a Newsletter platform. The XR5.0 Dissemination team uses the Mailchimp platform. Mailchimp is a polished, professional platform designed to help make campaigns. The actual newsletter editing takes place in a clean, web app.

Figure 20 - Mailchimp Account.

Newsletters aim to raise awareness and share relevant and valuable information and results to the XR5.0 mailing list. Additionally, keeping stakeholders informed on topics such as new blog posts, upcoming events, and any other relevant updates related to the project constitutes a high priority throughout the project duration.

In addition to that, the XR5.0 Project ensures high visibility of the newsletter sign-up on the homepage of its website. Furthermore, as part of the thought-out social media strategy, targeted posts are strategically crafted to include a compelling call to action, encouraging users to subscribe to the XR5.0 Newsletters mailing list. Notably, the newsletter itself embodies the project's distinct visual layout, reinforcing its brand identity and maintaining a cohesive user experience. These efforts effectively facilitate the dissemination of crucial project updates and relevant information to the engaged community.

3.4 Projects Announcements

The dissemination of project announcements on both the project's official website and the websites of its partner organizations plays a pivotal role in enhancing the project's visibility. These announcements serve as effective tools to engage a wider range of audiences. The project will strategically share updates and progress on various platforms, the project can attract attention from stakeholders, industry experts, and potential collaborators. Key to this process will be the publication and reposting of XR5.0 content to the websites of the project partners and to platforms/communities where the partners' participate. Table 1 presents a snapshot of this project, with a project announcement being reposted and/or published on different partners' websites.

Table 1 - XR5.0 Announcements.

Placement	Quotation
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<p>XR5.0 website</p>	<p>News</p> <p>XR5.0</p> <p>Kick of meeting</p> <p>Milan, Italy</p> <p>February 20-21, 2024</p> <p>🕒 February 21, 2024</p> <p>XR5.0 Kick-Of-Meeting</p>	
<p>UBITECH website</p>	<p>UBITECH VIRTUAL SOLUTIONS</p> <p>Company ▾ Services ▾ Solutions ▾ Research ▾ Case Studies ▾</p> <p>Posted on February 21, 2024 by ubitech</p> <p>UBITECH kicks off the XR5.0 Research and Innovation Action on human-centric, AI-enabled XR applications for Industry 5.0</p> <p>XR5.0 UBITECH participates at the kick-off meeting hosted by GFT (February 20 & 21, 2024) in Milan, Italy of the XR5.0: "Human-Centric AI-Enabled Extended Reality Applications for the Industry 5.0 Era" Innovation Action, officially started on January 1st, 2024. The project is funded by the European Commission (Grant Agreement No. 101135209) and spans on the period January 2024 – December 2026. XR5.0 will build, demonstrate, and validate a novel Person-Centric and AI-based XR paradigm that will be tailored to the requirements and nature of IS.0 applications. In this direction, the project will specify structuring principles and blueprints for using XR in IS.0 applications with emphasis on the development of innovative "XR-made-in-Europe" technology that blends with human-centric manufacturing technologies and adheres to European values.</p>	
<p>CORCOM website</p>	<p>CORCOM joins EU Horizon project on Extended Realities (XR)</p> <p>October 28, 2023 AI, data protection, data security, EUprojects, GDPR, Industry5.0, privacy, VR, XR</p> <p>CORCOM just received a new grant from the EU Commission to join the XR5.0 Horizon project. The project aims to create a person-centric and AI-based Extended Reality (XR) paradigm tailored for Industry 5.0 applications. It focuses on the integration of "XR-made-in-Europe" technology with human-centric manufacturing principles in line with European values. The project leverages human-centered digital twins and advanced AI paradigms to offer ergonomic and personalized training via a cloud-based XR platform. XR5.0 is developing six high-TRL pilot applications in areas such as AI-based product design and workers' training, all of which will be integrated into the EU XR platform and demonstrated in real-world manufacturing environments. The initiative is also fostering a community of stakeholders to ensure the sustainability and broader adoption of its innovative solutions, positioning the technologies for immediate commercialization. CORCOM will oversee all the legal and ethical aspects of the project.</p>	

<p>Aktuelles website</p>	<p>XR5.0 Human-Centric AI-Enabled Extended Reality Applications for the Industry 5.0 Era</p> <p>🕒 1. January 2024 👤 escribano 💬 0 Comments</p> <p>We proudly announce the the launch of our new project, XR5.0 (Human-Centric AI-Enabled Extended Reality Applications for the Industry 5.0 Era – GA 101135209), starting on the first of January 2024 with 24 other partners.</p> <p>The project is a Research and Innovation Action funded by the European Commission's research framework programme Horizon 2020, under the focus area "Emerging enabling technologies".</p>
<p>ATB website</p>	<p>ATB Home Competencies / Research Projects References News Contact 🔍</p> <p>XR5.0</p> <p>XR5.0 will build, demonstrate, and validate a novel Person-Centric and AI-based XR paradigm that will be tailored to the requirements and nature of 5.0 applications. In this direction, the project will specify structuring principles and blueprints for using XR in 5.0 applications with emphasis on the development of innovative "XR-made-in-Europe" technology that blends with human-centric manufacturing technologies and adheres to European values. The XR5.0 applications will consider the characteristics and context of the worker based on the integration of human-centred digital twins (DTs) that comprise the "digital image" of the worker. At the same time, XR5.0 will design and implement a unique blending of XR technology and advanced AI paradigms, including AI technologies that foster the interplay between humans and AI such as explainable AI (XAI), Active Learning (AL), Generative AI (GenAI), and neurosymbolic learning. The XR5.0 technologies will be coupled with a cloud-based XR training platform for Operator 5.0 applications, which will enable ergonomic and personalized training of industrial workers on popular processes. The XR5.0 paradigm will empower the development of six (6) novel high-TRL pilot applications spanning the areas of AI-based product design, remote and intelligent maintenance of assets, workers' training, support in product assembly, as well as guidance and instructions for troubleshooting. These applications will be demonstrated in realistic manufacturing environments. Moreover, they will be integrated to the EU XR platform to be</p>

4. CONTENT STRATEGY

4.1 Content Marketing KPIs

The following tables (Table 2, Table 3) provide an overview of the dissemination and communication actions for the XR5.0 project throughout its three-year duration. It also lists KPIs associated with these actions. These tables serve as valuable resources to outline the project's outreach efforts and ensure effective communication with stakeholders, partners, and the target audience. Note that these tables are part of the XR5.0 GA/DoA and will serve as contractual targets to be accomplished within the project.

Table 2 - Dissemination KPIs.

Dissemination Measure	Reason	Engagement Action	Target KPI
[D1] Organisation/attendance to conferences/workshops	Attract adopters, promote XR5.0	Organised: 4, Attended >=8	>=300 visitors, 4 speakers
[D2] Common activities with affiliated projects	Share knowledge	Common workshops, dissemination actions	3 common events, 4 posts in CORDIS/other EC systems
[D3] Workshop/collaborative schemas with similar projects	Devise common tools. Engage members	2 workshops	8 project synergies, 3 common products/services
[D4] Industry links, synergies	Attract adopters/users	10 real market links	3 adopters, 3 trials/testers
[D5] Open access exhibitions and demonstration events	Outreach non-specialised audiences	Demonstrate UC in lively/lightweight way	>=2 exhibitions, >=1 demo days, >=80 attendees
[D6] Onsite UC promotional demonstrations/workshops	Attract customers, Raise awareness	Short video media coverage, feedback	>=1 demonstration per UC >=1 workshops per UC
[D7] Online and/or F2F training/webinars on UCs	Ensure general public understands benefits	Non-IT savvy public & for Orgs	>=8 webinar/trainings >=30 attendees
[D8] Promotion of Results on the Future of Work	Engage Decision Makers and Investors	Open day with UC and media presence	>=2 events / workshops
[D9] F2F with Policymakers (National & EU level)	Engage policy makers	Open day with Use Cases	>=2 events, >=4 speakers

[D10] Promote XR5.0 Platform and Tools	Feedback on project tools and services	Activate all partner and UCs networks	>=30 testers of results, >=7 links to related web sites/portal
[D11] Uptake by Start-Ups & with example Use Cases	Raise awareness, attract users, receive feedback	F2F & online examples of provided material	10 synergies established
[D12] Open access reports	Scientific support	Scientific publications	>=3 journals, >=10 conference
[D13] Non-scientific reports	Adoption by SMEs	Trainings/Showcases	>=3 industry magazines
[D14] Standardisation liaisons	WG links, feedback	Common publications	Standards/organisations >=3
[D15] Association liaisons	Engage end users,	XR5.0 Webinars	Liaisons >5
[D16] Share results with the European R&D community	Maximise results' reuse and uptake	Upload project's results to the AI4EU platform (or its successor)	>=8 assets in Portal; >=2 workflows as Experiments

Table 3 - Communication KPIs.

Communication Measure	Reason	Engagement Action	Target KPI
[C1] Project website with links to XR5.0	Ensure back-links/ recognition to website	Engage registrants, Recurring visits	>=1000 visits, >200 registers >=250 blog interactions
[C2] Web/social content, blogposts, articles, whitepapers	Build visibility and community	Project progress events, news	Y1: >2/month, Y2: >3/month Y3: >4/month
[C3] Live audience feedback and live survey in online event	Grow community, Regular engagement	Visibility of project in all channels	1 live audience survey in online event >= 40 responders
[C4] Digital liaisons with human-AI initiatives	XR5.0 to be a part of DIH	Link with Clusters	>=15 backlinks to website >=7 common articles/posts
[C5] Videos, YouTube channel	Visually engage users	Promo video of UCs	1 promo/UC/tool, total >=10
[C6] social media: ResearchGate LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, etc.	Digital presence, new leads for synergies	Identify and regularly publish new content	>=1500 followers, >=300 posts, >=3000 interactions
[C7] Marketing pack and promotional press kit	Focused material (for stakeholders/events)	Exhibition, demo days, workshops	Rollup, brochure, banner, factsheet (interim and final)

[C8] Project identity and branding	Achieve recognition and brand awareness	All F2F meetings and all events	Logo, colour-space, artboard, graphic visuals, pitch, e-card
[C9] Press releases, newsletters, and digital briefs	Send tailored messages to specific audiences	Communicate project's benefits	Y1: >=2, Y2: >=4 (1/UC) Y3: >=10 (1/UC + 1/tool)
[C10] Stakeholders' database and engagement tracker	Prospective clients	Develop a database of contacts and liaisons	Y1: >=250, Y2: >=500, Y3: >=1000

4.2 Target Audience

The target audience of the XR5.0 project refers to the specific groups who are expected to express interest in the project's results. These target groups are crucial for the project's success and play a significant role in achieving its objectives. Figure 21 illustrates the identified target audience that the XR5.0 project aims to engage and interact with throughout its duration. XR5.0 will reach and communicate with these target audiences, to effectively disseminate information, gather feedback, and foster collaborations. The various dissemination activities of the project are appropriate for targeting all the list audiences and target groups. For instance, scientific publications and presentations provide an excellent means for disseminating the project's results to researchers, while participation in exhibitions and trade fairs will be one of the preferred ways to interact with manufacturers and integrators of industrial solutions.

Figure 21 - XR5.0 Target Audiences – Audience Persona(s).

4.3 Content Trackers

Three distinct content calendars have been developed to effectively communicate the XR5.0 project's message through various communication channels. These calendars serve as essential tools for partners to

provide comprehensive information on their upcoming blog posts, participation in events, conferences, meetings, and any other relevant actions related to the XR5.0 project.

The calendars are presented in Figure 22, Figure 23, Figure 24 below and feature multiple columns to capture important details. These include the topic and keywords of each blog post, the title, location, and participants of events, and comprehensive information regarding each activity, such as its type, KPIs, and explanatory notes.

These content calendars are integral for planning, coordinating, and documenting the project's communication efforts. By utilizing them effectively, partners can ensure consistency and alignment in disseminating project updates and showcasing the impact and progress of the XR5.0 project.

Blog Posts													
Dates	Partner	FINAL Deadline	DATE that has been sent it to INNOV-ACTS	SUGGESTED TOPIC or TITLE of the BLOG POST	Final Title (when ready)	Mini Summary or a Subtitle of the BLOG POST	3-5 keywords about the BLOG POST	Permission of Partner to be tagged at Social Media	LinkedIn Account & Link	Twitter Account & Link	Partner in Charge	RELEVANT WP (if applicable)	STATUS
March 2024	INNOV-ACTS Limited (INNOV)	26.3.2024		On XR and LLMs Convergence									
March 2024	Scuola Universitaria Professionale della Svizzera Italiana (SUPSI)	26.3.2024		Personalizing XR Applications with Digital Twins	Personalizing XR Applications and Human-Robot Interaction with Digital Twins		Human digital twins, human-robot collaboration, Operator4.0, Industry5.0	Yes	Elias Montini Vincenzo Cutrona Emanuele Fagnano Davide Matteri SUPSI DTI		SUPSI	wp3	draft reac
April 2024	CRL (IPIA)	12.3.2024		Guidelines for Designing Industrial Scale XR solutions									
April 2024	CYENS Centre of Excellence (CYENS)	12.3.2024		XRZED and XRS.0 Projects Overview and Potential Synergies									
May 2024	oculavis GmbH (OCU)	14.5.2024		Overview of the AR-enabled SHARE solution for Remote Maintenance									
May 2024	Switzerland Innovation Park Biel/Bienne AG (ISF)	14.5.2024		XR as an enabler for effective industrial training									
June 2024	UBITECH Ltd (UBI)	13.6.2024		Standards-based XR Architectures for Industrial use Cases									

Figure 22 - Blog post Tracker.

EVENTS TRACKER												
Partner	Date of complete the tracker	Title of event	Place & date of realisation	Type of Event	Title of presentation	Type of presentation	Number of participants	Type of audience addressed	Proposed text for social media	Proposed text for the website	Relevant @Tags/#Hashtags	Link to already published material, if any (on the partner's side)
GFT Italia S.r.l. (GFT)		KOM										

Figure 23 - Events Tracker.

Table 5 - Planned blog posts

Date	Partner	Indicative Topic
14.5.2024	OCU	Overview of the AR-enabled SHARE solution for Remote Maintenance
14.5.2024	SSF	XR as an enabler for effective industrial training
13.6.2024	UBI	Standards-based XR Architectures for Industrial use Cases
13.6.2024	LXS	Solutions for Managing XR data and the XR5.0 Approach
12.7.2024	TOG	A List of standards for Industrial XR Applications
12.7.2024	GFT	A Blog on XR Technologies
8.8.2024	KUKA	The XR5.0 Use Case for Industrial Robots
8.8.2024	TAP	AR/VR Training in Aircraft Maintenance
12.9.2024	SIE	XR Standards for Industrial Use Cases
12.9.2024	SPACE	Network Infrastructures for XR Applications
10.10.2024	SH	XR benefits in Industrial Maintenance
10.10.2024	EKSO	Training Challenges for Smart Pipes Manufacturing Workers
11.11.2024	HOLO	The role of an XR Streaming Platform for Industrial Training
11.11.2024	IML	IML's VR/AR solutions for industrial use cases
5.12.2024	UBI	AI and XR solutions integration
5.12.2024	UNP	UNP's Learning Center Platform for XR tutorials
15.1.2025	ATB	XR solutions for industrial training
15.1.2025	ALMER	ALMER's XR Solution for Remote Maintenance

5. PLANNING OF DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

5.1 Overview

Following paragraphs illustrate the dissemination activities planned by the project up to June 2025. A variety of different dissemination activities are planned in-line with the DoA and in order to reach the identified target audiences. All XR5.0 partners will engage in the implementation of the various activities including for example publications, organization of webinars, participation in exhibitions, training sessions and more. We have strived to make the plan as concrete and detailed as possible. Nevertheless, it is also acknowledged that there is always some uncertainty in terms of some of the planned events, publications and other activities. Hence, the planned activities should be seen as candidate activities that will be implemented with high likelihood. XR5.0 is likely to revise some of the planned activities e.g., to replace conference venues with others and to change the scope and content of some of the planned activities. Any revisions to the planned activities will be reported in the next deliverable of WP7 i.e., D7.1 which is due M12 (i.e., December 2024).

The project has already prepared a publication for the No. 137 of the ERCIM (European Research Consortium for Informatics and Mathematics) News (April 2024). The paper information follows:

“XR5.0: Human-Centric AI-Enabled Extended Reality Applications for the Industry 5.0 Era” by John Soldatos (INNOV-ACTS Limited), Georgios Makridis (University of Piraeus Research Center) and Fotis Liarokapis (CYENS Centre of Excellence), ERCIM News No. 137, April 2024.

5.2 Initial Plan for Scientific Publications

The provision of scientific publications holds particular importance in the XR5.0 project. Respecting the KPIs throughout the project's three-year timeframe, a minimum of thirteen scientific publications will be published. This includes three or more journal publications and 10 or more conference publications. The scientific publication activities will be led by the research and university partners of the consortium (e.g., UPRC, ATB, CYENS, SUPSI, IPIA). Moreover, other partners (e.g., research intensive SMEs like INNOV and LXS) will contribute to publications in collaboration with the academic partners. Others (e.g., IML) will be contributing to scientific review and tutorials focusing on the state-of-the-art analysis and providing a critical analysis of user experience and efficacy in XR-based training applications.

Table 6 below outlines the initial plan until the M18 of the project for scientific conferences with indicative dates, when available and Table 7 presents the initial plan for the scientific journals. The table indicate the partners that are already exploring or planning the participation in these conferences.

Table 6 – XR5.0 Initial Plan for Scientific Conferences (M1-M18) (Indicative List)

NO.	Scientific Conference	URL	Indicative dates	Partners
1	CaiSe (International Conference on Advanced Information Systems Engineering,	https://link.springer.com/conference/caise	2024/2025 Editions to be Announced	UBI
2	International Conference on Knowledge Based and Intelligent information and Engineering Systems	http://kes2024.kesinternational.org/	11-13 September, 2024	ATB

3	IEEE International Conference on Industrial Informatics (INDIN)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/conhome/1001443/all-proceedings	2024/2025 Editions to be Announced	ATB
4	International Conference on Intelligent Decision Technologies	http://idt-24.kesinternational.org/	19-21 June, 2024	ATB
5	IEEE, 10th International Conference on Virtual Reality (Bournemouth, United Kingdom)	https://icvr.org/index.html	24-26 July, 2024	UPRC
6	Springer, 8th Edition of the Worlds4 (London, United Kingdom) -	https://worlds4.co.uk/	23-26 July, 2024	UPRC
7	IFIP Conference on Advances in Production Management Systems (APMS) 2024	https://www.apms-conference.org/	8 September, 2024	SUPSI
8	IEEE International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (EFTA 2024)	https://2024.ieee-etfa.org/	10-13, September 2024	SUPSI
9	58th CIRP Conference on Manufacturing Systems (CIRP-CMS 2025)	https://cirp-cms2025.org/	2024/2025 Edition to be Announced	SUPSI
10	9th IFAC Symposium on Information Control Problems in Manufacturing (INCOM 2024 IFAC-INCOM 2025)	https://www.ifac-control.org/conferences/@@conference_view	/2025 Edition to be Announced	SUPSI
11	ACM Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology (VRST)	https://vrst.acm.org/	9-11 October, 2024	SPACE
12	International Conference on Augmented and Virtual Reality (AVR)	https://dl.acm.org/conference/icvars	September 4-7, 2024	SPACE

Table 7- XR5.0 Initial Plan for Scientific Journal (M1-M18) (Indicative List)

N0.	Scientific Journals	URL	Partners
1	Journal: Manufacturing Letters	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/manufacturing-letters	UBI
2	Springer Link, Virtual Reality Journal	https://link.springer.com/journal/10055?sap-outbound-id=180B7004687E398098728165A4178131BFF1E3C3	UPRC
3	IEEE Access	https://ieeaccess.ieee.org	CYENS

4	Legal Journal: Computer & Security Law Review	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/computer-law-and-security-review#:~:text=The%20Computer%20Law%20and%20Security.IT%20law%20and%20computer%20security.	CORCOM
5	Legal Journal: International Review of Law, Computers & Technology	https://www.tandfonline.com/toc/cirl20/current	CORCOM
6	Legal Journal: European Data Protection Law Review (EDPL)	https://www.lexnion.eu/en/journals/edpl/#:~:text=The%20European%20Data%20Protection%20Law%20Review%20(EDPL)%20provides%20a%20practical,in%20the%20EU%20Member%20States.	CORCOM
7	Legal Journal: Journal of AI Law and Regulation, the Springer book series Perspective in Law	N/A	CORCOM
8	Legal Journal: Business and Innovation, and more	N/A	CORCOM
9	IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=2945	SPACE

Moreover, a list of relevant conferences that represent publication opportunities for the project has been completed and circulated to the partners, as illustrated in Table 8.

Table 8 – Initial List of XR5.0 Related Events (XR and AI focused) (M1-M18)

Date	Conference	Link	Location
11-12 July, 2024	The Global Insight Conference on Artificial Intelligence (GICAI)	https://gic-ai.org/	Paris, France
4-7 September 2024	International Conference on eXtended Reality XR SALENTO 2024	https://www.xrsalento.it/index	Lecce, Italy
17-20 September, 2024	The International Conference on Multimedia Computing, Networking and Applications (MCNA2024)	https://mcna-conference.org/2024/	Valencia, Spain
20-22 September, 2024	International Conference on Haptics and Virtual Reality (ICHVR 2024)	https://www.ichvr.org/	Barcelona, Spain
29-30 October, 2024	AWE EU 2024	https://www.awexr.com/eu-2024/	Vienna, Austria
9-10-11 December 2024	Stereopsia	https://stereopsia.com/	Brussels, Belgium

The dissemination manager of the project will continually update the above lists and will communicate to partners relevant publications opportunities.

5.3 Workshops and Collaborations in Events

Workshops play a vital role in fostering collaboration and facilitating knowledge exchange. Workshops can bring together various stakeholders, including project partners, experts, policymakers, and end-users, to come together and engage in targeted discussions, problem-solving exercises, and skill-building activities.

The XR5.0 partners plan to participate in a rich set of workshops, while at the same time making plans to organize or co-organize workshops where the project’s results can be presented. In this direction, workshop organization activities that are already undertaken by the partners will be exploited. For instance, SH plans approximately 15 – 20 workshops until M18 (June 2025), in collaboration with the pilot partner OCU. Some of these workshops will provide opportunities for disseminating the developments of SH and OCU in the XR5.0 project. Moreover, the legal partner of the consortium (COR) plans to organize workshops focusing on key legislations such as the EU AI Act, along with its intersections with GDPR and emerging cybersecurity laws. These workshops will be tailored for legal professionals and IT specialists involved in navigating compliance landscapes, including software developers. COR is already preparing the first workshop event in Reykjavik, Iceland. SSF will organize several workshops about digital lean with external companies or students. The upcoming workshop is performed multiple times pro year. In this workshop, ALMER’s glasses are used to help the coordination between the logistics and the production. The logistician can see where the different packages are waiting to be picked up and where to bring them. SSF estimates that will organize/ participate in approximately 45 workshops until M18. XR5.0 will be presented in some of them.

Internal workshops will also take place, as KUKA plans to spread information about the project and collect ideas to streamline the project goals with the challenges of day-to-day work.

Table 9 outlines the planning of upcoming workshops in which the partners will organize or participate until M18. However, this list will be regularly updated to reflect any changes or additions.

Table 9 - Partners' workshops/ collaborative schemas with similar project planning.

No	Workshop	URL	Indicative Dates	Partner(s)
1	IEEE International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR)	https://www.ismar.net/	21-25 October, 2024	SPACE
2	ACM Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI)	https://dl.acm.org/conference/chi	11-16 May, 2024	SPACE
3	AAR (All about Remote) Interactive Workshop	https://allaboutremote.com/en/	5 December, 2024	OCU
4	Open Conf (2025)	https://www.open-conf.gr	2025 Edition to be announced	IML
6	16th International Conference on Disability, Virtual Reality & Associated Technologies	N/A	2025 Edition to be announced	IML
7	Workshops organized in the context of IEEE VR Conference	https://ieeervr.org/	8-12 March, 2025	UBI

8	Knowledge Graph Alliance (KGA) General Assembly Meeting – April 18th, 202	https://www.kg-alliance.org/general-assembly-2024/	18 April, 2024	ATB
9	1st KG-AI Summit by the Knowledge Graph Alliance (KGA)	https://emmc.eu/events/1st-kg-ai-summit-apr-19-2024/	19 April 2024	ATB
10	Participate in the meetings of the KGA Working Group “Explainable-AI-ready data and metadata principles”	https://www.kg-alliance.org/event-wg-announcement/	19 March 2024	ATB
11	ACM Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI) 2025	https://chi.acm.org/chi-series/	2025 Edition to be Announced	CYENS
12	ACM Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology (VRST) 2025	https://vrst.acm.org/	2025 Edition to be Announced	CYENS
13	TOG hosted Conference: Ecosystems Architecture and AI Standards, Edinburgh, UK ¹	N/A	22-25 April 2024	TOG
14	TOG hosted Conference: Enterprise Digitalization (working title)	N/A	28-31 October 2024, USA	TOG
15	TOG hosted Conference: Title and Location to be decided,	N/A	April 2025	TOG

5.4 Clustering and Joint Activities with Related Projects

XR5.0 plans to collaborate closely with other prominent EU-Funded projects that focus on Extended Reality (XR). In this direction, the project has already initiated interactions with such relevant projects towards identifying synergies and collaborative activities. Table 10 presents an initial list of related projects that have been identified by the XR5.0 project, along with information about initial interactions and collaboration with these projects. The project plans to establish collaborations with more projects. This means that Table 10 will periodically updated to reflect any new collaborations that arise during the three-year duration of the project. Additionally, Table 11 displays the meetings that have been already done with the related projects.

Table 10 - Joint Activities with Related Projects

Project Name/ Number	Project Description	Collaboration Strategy
XR4ED (https://xr4ed.eu/) HEU GA No. 101093159	The EU-funded XR4ED project explores the use of the extended reality (XR) industry, which has evolved and maintained a leading role globally in software and content production. Specifically, it investigates	XR5.0 has already interacted with XR4ED through the common partners (e.g., CYENS). An initial set of synergies has been specified as part of these interactions including: (i) Regularly uploading and reposting content as part of cross marketing actions between

¹ Launch of XR5.0 will be presented

	learning resources and advantages of learning using XR. The project also set up a one-stop-shop and open marketplace for XR applications for learning, training and education.	the two projects; (ii) Planning of collaborative workshops and webinars to foster knowledge sharing and collective growth.
XR2Learn (https://xr2learn.eu/) HEU GA No. 101092851	Virtual, augmented or mixed reality (VR/AR/MR) – in general extended reality (XR) – provides numerous benefits in education. XR increases the knowledge area, offers active experience rather than just passive information, helps to understand complex concepts, subjects or theories, prevents distractions during the study, boosts creativity and expands learners’ efficiency in gaining knowledge.	XR5.0 has already initiated synergies and collaborations with XR2Learn, following interactions between the dissemination leaders of the two projects and between XR5.0 and the XR2Learn Community Manager. The scope of the two project’s collaborations includes: (i) Cross-marketing activities including mutual sharing and reposting of content items; (ii) Community building activities (e.g., joint trainings and webinars); (iii) Regular experience sharing regarding architectural issues and use cases.
OpenVerse (https://www.openverse.eu/) HEU GA No: 101135701	The aim of OPENVERSE is to contribute to laying the foundations of such a European Metaverse by establishing a knowledge base on it, setting up and animating a community of stakeholders, testing a methodology that combines user co-creation and XR in real world cases of industrial and societal relevance, exploring relevant ethical, legal, IPR and governance challenges, and producing industry standards as well as a technology and policy roadmap and recommendations to guide the future establishment of the Open Metaverse concept in Europe and worldwide.	XR5.0 has not yet initiated interactions with OpenVerse. However, such meetings and interactions are planned during the next weeks. The envisaged collaboration plan includes the provision of insights and value added technical contents from XR5.0 to OpenVerse in order to be disseminated to the OpenVerse community i.e., XR5.0 plans to use the OpenVerse CSA as a dissemination multiplier. Furthermore, the project will attempt to organize joint events and webinars with the OpenVerse, including activities with policy and regulatory development content.
XR2Industry HEU GA No: 101135547	XR2Industry priorities are: data privacy, empowerment, industrial relevance, openness. XR2Industry gathers 9 partners, supports 12 third parties, and through advisory board and clustering activities, will leverage impact all over Europe.	The XR2Industry is the project that will develop the XR platform/marketplace that will integrate the XR5.0 “XR made in Europe” technologies. XR5.0 aims to establish a close collaboration with XR2Industry on architecture alignment and knowledge sharing activities.

Table 11 - Joint Activities / Telcos with Related projects

Project Name/ Number	Date of the meeting	Next steps
XR4ED (https://xr4ed.eu/)	March 7, 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Next meeting: May 7, 2024 ● Cross-marketing strategy on social media ● Planning a joint workshop or

HEU GA No. 101093159		webinar for XR4ED and XR5.0
XR2Learn (https://xr2learn.eu/) HEU GA No. 101092851	23 April, 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross marketing actions (social media) • XR2Learn has created a community forum: https://forum.xr2learn-marketplace.eu/. XR5.0 will participate in this • A telco with XR4ED and XR2Learn will take place next months. • Community building • Create common publications/ whitepapers

In general, a collaborative approach with related projects offers a prime opportunity for the exchange of knowledge, insights, and best practices. The sharing of the various projects’ unique experiences, expertise, and perspectives provides a sound basis for creating an enriched pool of collective knowledge. Joint activities like workshops and seminars, will help stakeholders to acquire valuable insights and expertise. Moreover, the forging of alliances between related projects will amplify the impact and extends the reach of each individual project. This collaboration will enable projects to leverage each other’s networks and dissemination channels.

XR5.0 has developed a structured approach to foster such collaborations. Prior to interactions for kickstarting these collaborations, an initial strategic agenda has been formulated, encompassing essential actions to facilitate joint activities with related projects. The agenda includes a list of candidate activities that could foster common collaboration goals (e.g., cross-marketing activities and organization of collaborative workshops or webinars). Regular communication calls are also planned for continuous reporting and coordination of the collaborative activities.

5.5 Exhibitions and demonstration events

Once the XR5.0 project reaches a certain level of maturity, a series of exhibitions and demonstration events will be conducted. These events are organized to showcase the project’s outcomes to a diverse audience, including the general public and stakeholders. Exhibitions will provide an excellent channel for reaching manufacturers, developers and integrators of industrial automation solutions, XR/AI integrators and other industrial organizations. Moreover, they will offer an excellent channel for product-oriented enterprises of the consortium (including the XR vendors of the consortium) to showcase the enhancements to their products that will be implemented in XR5.0, as well as the use of these projects in XR5.0 use cases.

Bi-annual in-person conferences hosted by TOG in Europe and the USA and quarterly virtual conferences will continue after the XR5.0 project reaches a maturity level and these can include XR5.0 presentations/demonstrations. Table 12 illustrates the initial plan for participation in exhibitions and demonstrations. Like in the case of other activities, this plan will be continuously reviewed, refined, and enhanced as the project progresses, ensuring the inclusion of any relevant updates or improvements. Note that the exhibition plans include both international events and local events (e.g., open days) organized by the project partners.

Table 12 - Partners’ Exhibitions and Demonstration events plan.

NO	Exhibitions/ demonstration events	URL	Dates	Partner
1	Consumer Electronics Show (CES)	https://www.ces.tech/	2025	SPACE

2	Augmented World Expo (AWE)	https://www.awexr.com/	18-20 June, 2024	SPACE
3	ACHEMA 2024	https://www.achema.de/en/the-achema/overview	10 -14 June, 2024	SH
4	LAB-SUPPLY Fairs in Berlin	https://www.tradefairdates.com/LAB-SUPPLY-M11149/Berlin.html	18 June, 2024	SH
5	LAB-SUPPLY Fairs in Innsbruck	https://www.analytik-jena.com/company/events/exhibitions-conferences-webseminars/lab-supply-innsbruck/	4 September, 2024	SH
6	drinktec Munich	https://drinktec.com/en-US/home	15-19 Septeber, 2024	SH
7	LAB-Supply 2025	-	events and dates to be determined	SH
8	LAB-Supply 2026	-	events and dates to be determined	SH
9	AAR (All About Remote): Demo Booth: Showing outcomes developed within the XR5.0 research project	https://allaboutremote.com/en/	5 December, 2024	OCU
10	Augmented World Expo - AWE Europe (2026).	https://www.awexr.com/	18-20 June, 2024	IML
11	XR training demonstration for the SYNFIELD ² solutions using the XR5.0 platform in Agrotica exhibition.	https://www.agrotica-expo.gr/en/	29 January, 2026 – 1 February, 2026	SYN
12	Global Industrie	https://www.global-industrie.com/en/home	11-14 March, 2025	UBI
13	Hannover Messe	https://www.hannovermesse.de/en	22-26 April, 2024	UBI
14	Psychology Conference taking place at the Piaget Institute in Lisbon ³	N/A	May 2024	IPIA
15	CYENS Open Days/ CYENS internal events.	N/A	To be announced	CYENS
16	Open-days, Open-laboratories	N/A	To be announced	SUPSI
17	Mini-Factory visits	https://minifactory.spslab.ch/	To be announced	SUPSI

² precision agriculture solution which is the main product of SYN

³ attended by all psychology undergraduate students and faculty members, as well as students from other faculties.

18	Hannover Messe	https://www.hannovermesse.de/en	22-26 April, 2024	ALMER
19	International Smart Factory Summit 2024 ⁴	N/A	12-14 June, 2024	SSF
20	SSF hosts its Breakfast Pitch, where 5 Partners presents their solutions about a smart factory topic ⁵ .	N/A	4 times a year; Dates to be Announced	SSF
21	During the year SSF performs tours of its TEF. During this tour the XR possibilities are explained and showcased in our factory.	N/A	Approximately 30 tours will be performed until M18; Dates to be Announced	SSF
22	SIAMS Fair	https://www.siams.ch/The-trade/The-show	N/A	SSF
23	EPAJ Fair	https://ephj.ch/en/	N/A	SSF
24	SINDEX Fair	https://www.tradefairdates.com/SINDEX-M9602/Bern.html	2.9.2025 - 4.9.2025	SSF
25	SIAMS in Moutier	https://www.tradefairdates.com/SIAMS-M4967/Moutier.html	16-19 April, 2024	LNS
26	MACH in Birmingham	https://www.tradefairdates.com/MACH-M5266/Birmingham.html#:~:text=In%20summary%2C%20MACH%20at%20the.network%2C%20and%20explore%20business%20opportunities.	15-19 Aril, 2024	LNS
27	AMB in Stuttgart	https://www.expostandservice.com/amb-stuttgart/#:~:text=As%20one%20off%20the%20top,from%20all%20over%20the%20world.	10-14 September, 2024	LNS
28	US IMTS in Chicago	https://www.imts.com/	9-14 September, 2024	LNS
29	Japan JIMTOF in Tokyo	https://www.jimtof.org/en/	5 -10 November, 2024	LNS
30	LNS showrooms in Germany, France and Switzerland	N/A	2025 dates to be Announced	LNS

⁴ The conference will be hosted by SSF and will attract many international guests, members, industry specialists and research partners.

⁵ This event brings together 70 to 80 people from the industry every time.

5.6 Training/ webinars

Table 13 presents an initial list of trainings and webinars that will be organized and/or participated in by the XR5.0 partners throughout the project's duration. This list is subject to updates as new events may arise during the three-year timeline of the project. Several partners will not organize any training or webinars for the following months as the project's results will be in their infancy. However, selected partners like UBI plan internal (consortium-wide) training sessions to train partners on the XR5.0 architecture and technologies. Joint training webinars with other parties (e.g., consortium partners of other projects in the cluster) may be also organized to share insights into the system design aspects. Also, SSF performs multiple Certificate of Advanced Studies (CAS) for professionals in the industry who want to improve their knowledge about, for example, industry 4.0. In this topic, the use case of XR and the possibilities the modern technologies provide will be also shown.

One more opportunity to share knowledge and expertise through a series of webinars is the pilot's focus on developing personalized XR training content for different skills. SPACE will explore opportunities for collaboration with other relevant EU-funded projects, leveraging synergies and amplifying the impact of XR5.0s results. These partnerships and joint initiatives foster knowledge transfer and increase the visibility and influence of the project within the research community.

Moreover, ALMER will showcase the possibilities that the XR project can bring to the workers and give the people the ability to test the system, thanks its partnership with SSF. In this direction, the AR glasses of the company and the XR5.0 project will be presented and used in different Use cases and workshops to demonstrate its advancements.

Table 13 - Partners' training and webinar plan.

NO	Training/ Webinars	URL	Indicative Dates	Partner
1	Training SCHMIDT + HAENSCH service technicians in the use of oculavis SHARE software and selected smartglasses for field studies in Q4/2024		Q4/2024	SH
2	XR5.0 partner-hosted workshops: Immersive Lives will organize a workshop in immersive technologies (VR/AR).	-		IML
3	2 training sessions already since M01	-	January 2024	LXS
4	2 training sessions per month, starting from May (M05). 1 for developers and 1 for administrators	-	May 2024	LXS
5	TOG hosts various communications channels for standards and industry technologies evolution topics including webinars, blogs, podcasts, and a YouTube channel: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Podcasts 	https://www.opengroup.org/our-podcasts https://publications.opengroup.org/webinars https://blog.opengroup.org/	N/A	TOG

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webinars • Blog • YouTube Channel 	https://www.youtube.com/user/theopengroup		
6	Leibniz University of Hannover (Germany)	https://www.uni-hannover.de/en/	N/A	COR
7	Webinars and Training Sessions to Vilnius University (Lithuania) and Copenhagen University	https://www.vu.lt/en/ and https://www.ku.dk/english/	N/A	COR

5.7 Open Access Strategy

The XR5.0 project publications will be published on the Zenodo website. Each publication will be assigned a unique DOI. The scientific publications will be made available in either the Gold Open Access or Green Open Access format. Furthermore, to ensure wider accessibility and visibility, all publications will not only be uploaded to the Zenodo open-access repository but will also be provided on the project's official website. Furthermore, in-line with the DoA, the following OA and Open Science measures and activities are planned:

- Early Access to XR5.0 results: XR5.0 will provide the scientific community with early access to the project's results, through providing them as informal publications to the most reputable online repositories, including the Computing Research Repository (CoRR) (a partnership of ACM, arXiv.org and others).
- Open Peer Review: XR5.0 will allow self-selected reviewers to provide comments on the project's scientific outputs (i.e., publications, blueprints), beyond reviewers selected by the Open Access journals (or other forums) where the results will be made available.
- Open Research Europe Publishing Platform (OREPP): XR5.0 will publish a minimum of two (≥ 2) articles in the OREPP, including one project overview article at the beginning of the project and/or a concluding article providing a summary of the project's main research achievements at the end of the project.
- Open-Source Software (OSS): Most of the developments of the academic partners will be made available at open-source software, which will be published in GitHub. The open-source strategy of the project foresees the offering of OSS results in a business-friendly way (i.e., in a way that makes it possible for third-party European enterprises to benefit from the project's results). XR5.0 commits to the selection of a business-friendly license to be agreed upon the parties for the open-source results of the project. Several XR5.0 partners (e.g., ATB, UBI, UPRC, INNOV) have a track record of OSS contributions and experience in managing OSS codebases and communities.
- Open Citizen Science - DIHs: The project will liaise with AI DIHs, PPP on AI, and relevant HEU projects where XR5.0's partners and their business networks have a strong presence (e.g., EFFRA, Platform Industrie4.0, Industry 2025, Adra, DAIRO, GAIA-X, IDSA). These activities will aim to engage XR and AI integrators, data providers, SMEs (including solution providers), and citizens in developing and using the project's results. The XR5.0 co-creation methodology will facilitate the engagement of third-party individuals, data providers, and policymakers in developing, validating, and evaluating the project's outcomes.
- Open Data and FAIR Data: The project's datasets, either real or synthetic ones, will be made available as open data in FAIR repositories. Similarly, the project will share AI models and data analysis flows in the XR5.0 and open repositories like OpenML based on standard formats like PMML (Predictive Model Markup Language) and ONNX.
- Open Science Policy Support: XR5.0 will offer policymakers and regulators with access to information and services of the XR5.-Apps, which will boost the development of XR and AI policies, in-line with the AI Act's timeline. The implementation of these practices will be led by the academic partners (e.g., IPIA,

UPRC, ATB), who have relevant experience and established open science procedures as part of their day-to-day operations.

5.8 Stakeholders Database

According to the KPIs established for the project, the development of a comprehensive database of contacts and liaisons is stipulated within the three-year project duration. This database will be one of the main tools for documenting the project's community, in-line with the targets of the community-building task (WP7/T7.4). To facilitate this objective, an engagement tracking process has been devised, which leads to the regular collection of stakeholders' interactions through all the different dissemination and communication channels (i.e., the touch points) of the project. The database encompasses various pertinent details including the individual's name, email address, the platform through which engagement occurred, their affiliated company, country of origin, job title, relevant sector, and organizational type. The database exclusively incorporates publicly available information sourced from platforms such as LinkedIn, X, Facebook, YouTube, and Newsletter Subscribers. As per the project's milestones, by the conclusion of the first year, a minimum of 250 contacts are expected to be logged in the database. At the time of writing of this document, more than 200 contacts have already been recorded, which indicates positive progress towards meeting this target. The stakeholders' database will be securely stored and used in-line with the GDPR principles (e.g., informed consent, minimal data collection).

6. XR5.0 CONTRIBUTIONS TO INDUSTRIAL ASSOCIATIONS, PROJECT CLUSTERS AND PRE-STANDARDIZATION

6.1 Standardization liaisons and activities

XR5.0 partner TOG is responsible for leading standardization liaisons and activities within the XR5.0 project. This crucial task primarily focuses on standardization, clustering, and policy-making activities related to the project. The work involves liaisons and participation with industrial associations (EFFRA, DAIRO, AIOTI), project clusters and initiatives (e.g., AI4Europe, AI4Manufacturing), national manufacturing initiatives (e.g., Platform Industrie4.0, Productech, Industry 2025), as well as SDOs (IEEE, ISO, CEN/CENELEC, ETSI). The project will contribute insights into pre-normative activities based on whitepapers, presentations to meetings of the above-listed initiatives, as well as participation in joint meetings and workshops. Standardization liaisons and activities provide information about standards used in XR5.0-ReferenceModel and as well as knowledge on how XR5.0 aligns with European laws, acts, and directives (Table 14).

Table 14 - Standardization liaisons and activities

Partners	Standards/Directive - Results Alignment	Contribution to XR5.0
CYENS, SUPSI	OpenXR i.e., Khronos Group open standard for access to VR/AR engines and devices including holographic devices and immersive VR devices	XR5.0 will use OpenXR for access to XR assets and devices as part of the UCs; It will propose extensions to the standard for interactions with Human-Centric XR-based DTs
TOG, UNP	Augmented Reality Framework from the ETSI Industry Specification Group (ISG ARF)	XR5.0 will consider the ISG ARF in the specification of the XR5.0-Reference Model and will propose enhancements
IPIA, TOG	XR Safety Initiative (XRSI) Standards	Used in the XR5.0 co-creation to ensure safety/security
GFT, TOG	JTC 1/SC 42, AI Architecture: Standardised Architecture for BigData and AI Systems	XR extensions to this architecture will be provided as part of the XR5.0-ReferenceModel specification through DAIRO
COR, GFT	AI Act / AI Regulation: Proposal for regulating AI systems, as put forward by the EP and the Council of Europe	XR5.0 systems will be assessed against their compliance to the AI Act based on the level of their risk for the worker; Feedback from the risk assessment will be provided to policy makers
UPRC, INNOV	IEEE P2976 Standard (XAI): Standard specifying the properties of an XAI model	XR5.0 will consider this standard in the specification of requirements for the XAI models to be considered in the project
	Open Standards for AI Model Interoperability: ONNX, OpenML, IEEE 2941-2021	XR5.0 will develop AI models based on these standards to facilitate their exchange, interoperability, and reuse across XR environments.

TOG, COR, IPIA	IEEE 7000 standards for ethical AI applications	XR5.0 will use IEEE 7000 based benchmarks
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Table 15 lists some additional collaborations with SDOs in standards-development topics.

Table 15 –Envisaged Collaboration with SDOs

SDO/ Association Liaisons/ Working Group	Scope of Liaison / Collaboration	Partners
IEEE Standards Association, the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C)	W3C standards will be considered in the design and development of the XR5.0 user interfaces	SPACE
Virtual Reality Industry Forum (VRIF)	XR5.0 will consult VRIF guidelines for video interfaces	SPACE
RAMI, Reference Architectural Model Industrie 4.0 ⁶	RAMI4.0 will be considered as a background reference model for the development of the XR5.0 architecture	UBI
IIRA Industrial Internet Reference Architecture (https://www.iiconsortium.org/iira/)	IIRA will be also among the background reference architectures that will be used to drive the development of the XR5.0 architecture	UBI
LASFA, LASim Smart Factory ⁷	LASFA will be also among the background reference architectures that will be used to drive the development of the XR5.0 architecture	UBI
SITAM, Stuttgart IT-Architecture for Manufacturing ⁸ and IVRAM, Industrial Value Chain Reference Architecture ⁹	SITAM and IVRAM will be also among the background reference architectures that will be used to drive the development of the XR5.0 architecture	UBI
Archimate for architecture design (https://www.archimatetool.com/)	For system engineering, we will use, adapt, and possibly extend aspects of this standard	UBI
Elements of TOGAF for architecture design (https://www.opengroup.org/togaf)	For system engineering, we will use, adapt, and possibly extend aspects of this standard	UBI
Elements of EIRA for interoperability (https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/european-interoperability-reference-architecture-eira)	For system engineering, we will use, adapt, and possibly extend aspects of this standard	UBI

The XR5.0 standardization lead maintains also close links and liaisons with several other XR5.0 related SDOs, including the Digital Twin Consortium (DTC), the Object Management Group (OMG), IEEE, ETSI, CEN/CENELEC, ISO/CD TS 81001-2-1 (Health software and health IT systems safety, effectiveness and

⁶ <https://www.isa.org/intech-home/2019/march-april/features/rami-4-0-reference-architectural-model-for-industr>

⁷ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360835221001455#b0355>

⁸ https://www.ipvs.uni-stuttgart.de/departments/as/downloadgallery_as/groegech/Kassner_Stuttgart_IT_Architecture_for_Manufacturing.pdf

⁹ (https://docs.iv-i.org/doc_161208_Industrial_Value_Chain_Reference_Architecture.pdf)

security – new standards for ensuring safety of connected embedded devices), ISO/IEC 20243-2:2023: Open trusted technology provider standard; the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) and the International Committee for Information Technology Standards (INCITS). As part of the implementation of the standardization task of the project, these links may be exploited to share/contribute XR5.0 outcomes once they become available. The project and TOG are in the process of identifying the most appropriate of these SDOs with respect to the expected outcomes of XR5.0. Updated information and planning will be reported in the scope of deliverable D7.2.

6.2 Liaisons with and Contributions to Industrial Associations

The EU partners will liaise with industrial associations at European level in order to contribute to their activities based on XR5.0 results. The scope of the contributions will include participation to events and meetings organized by the associations, preparation of joint papers or contribution to whitepapers of the associations, as well as collaboration with other members around the XR5.0 technologies and use cases. Moreover, the project will exploit the opportunities for liaising and collaborating with associations of the Swiss Manufacturing/Industry 5.0 ecosystem, thanks to the participation of the Associated (Swiss) partners in the XR5.0 consortium. For example, SSF will promote the project’s outcomes to its partners and members of its ecosystem in Switzerland (i.e., to approx. 3000 persons per year). Furthermore, SSF will establish liaisons and exchanges with clusters and initiatives in 3 other sectors: the Swiss Healthtech Center, the Swiss Battery Technology Center, and the Swiss Advanced Manufacturing Center. Also, SSF will engage with associations like the Lions Club and Industire 2025. Moreover, LNS is part of the Swissmem association, which has more than 1250 members in the mechanical and electrical engineering industries. It will therefore promote XR5.0 in this community.

Table 16 provides a list of collaborations with industrial associations that will be pursued by the partners. It is important to note that this list is not exhaustive and will undergo continuous updates and improvements as the XR5.0 project progresses and reaches higher levels of maturity.

Table 16 – Liaisons and Envisaged Collaboration with Industrial Associations

Industrial Association / Working Group	Scope of Collaboration	Partners
Data AI and Robotics (DAIRO)	Sharing of information about the XR5.0 architectures and its alignment to DAIRO (and BDVA) reference models; Participation in DAIRO organized/supported events like the Data Week and the EBDVF	GFT, UPRC
Alliance for IoT Innovation (AIOTI)	Participation in AIOTI sponsored events (e.g., IoT Week); Contribution to the AIOTI WG11 (IoT in Manufacturing) whitepapers/documents based on the use of XR in manufacturing	UNP,
European Factories of the Future Research Association (EFFRA)	Participation in EFFRA events, project clusters and exhibitions	UNP, SUPSI, NOVA
Energistics Consortium – standards for oil/gas energy production companies	TOG hosted SDO groupings that appear to be related to XR5.0 pilots and reference architectures.	TOG
Exploration, Mining, Metals & Minerals Forum	TOG hosted SDO groupings that appear to be related to XR5.0 pilots and reference architectures as the focus of the forum is on enterprise architecture standards and reference	TOG

	models for the exploration, mining, metals, and minerals industries	
Commercial Aviation Working Group – Commercial Aviation Reference Architecture	TOG hosted SDO groupings that appear to be related to XR5.0 pilots and reference architectures.	TOG
IT4IT Forum – Reference Architecture for managing the operations of IT in enterprise and government organisations	TOG hosted SDO groupings that appear to be related to XR5.0 pilots and reference architectures.	TOG
Enterprise Architecture Forum – TOGAF enterprise architecture methodology with over 100K certified IT architects around the world	TOG hosted SDO groupings addressing industry IT architecture methods and tools.	TOG
ArchiMate Forum – industry standard modelling language for enterprise architecture	TOG hosted SDO groupings addressing industry IT architecture methods and tools.	TOG
AITI Associazione Industrie Ticinesi, AGIRE, and Other EU initiatives that have AI in Industry 5.0 aspects (Circular Twain, BetterFactory, CIRCULOOS; KITT4SME, etc.)	Sharing of experience and results regarding AI and XR use cases in manufacturing; Joint meetings/workshops; Best practice sharing regarding the development of AI-based Digital Twins	SUPSI, NOVA

In-line with the DoA, the project will also establish liaisons with industrial associations at National Level, such as Platform Industrie 4.0 in Germany (ATB, KUKA) and ProduTech in Portugal (UNP, IPIA). The primary goal of these collaborations will be to raise awareness about XR5.0 and engage stakeholder at national level.

7. CONCLUSIONS, OUTLOOK, AND NEXT STEPS

This deliverable has presented the dissemination activities implemented by XR5.0 during the first four months of the project's lifetime. These activities have established the project's brand image, social media channels and content management/tracking tools. Moreover, an initial batch of dissemination materials and content (e.g., publications, blog posts) have been produced, and liaisons with relevant projects and industrial associations have been established. These activities provide a sound basis for implementing parts of the project's ambitious dissemination and communication plan. Most importantly, the present deliverable has provided a quite detailed plan for the dissemination and communication activities that will be carried by the project during the following months and up to M18 of the project. Moreover, the methodology to be followed and the types of activities that will be undertaken till the end of the project have been outlined, yet a more detailed plan up to M18 has been provided.

The presented plan includes a variety of dissemination and communication activities, including for example scientific publications in journals and conferences, organization of workshops, participation in various workshops, publishing of blog posts, regular production of newsletters, posts in social media, collaboration with other XR projects, participation in exhibitions and trade fairs, joint activities with industrial associations, as well as collaboration and contribution to SDOs (notably in terms of pre-normative standardization activities). It is important to underline that the deliverable presents an initial (yet detailed) version of the project's dissemination and communication plan, which may be subject to further enhancements and modifications as the project evolves. This is fully in-line with the project's agile and iterative approach to dissemination and communication.

In the coming months the project will implement several of the list activities. The next deliverable of WP7 of the project (i.e., D7.2, due M12/December 2024) will provide an updated report on the implemented activities. As part of D7.2, we also plan to report any updates and revisions to the presented plan. The project's dissemination activities will also strive to increase the amount of dissemination content and materials produced. Specifically, the content will be generated for different channels as follows:

- **YouTube Video Content:** The channels will be populated and enriched with videos of webinars, workshops, general videos of the project etc.
- **Social Media and Newsletters:** Regular social media posts will be created and published, along with newsletter campaigns. Social media posts regarding announcements, events, (intermediate and final) results, as well as blog posts and updates will be regularly published on all channels.
- **Website Updates:** Social media content and project results will also be published on the website, along with project documents like deliverables and publications.
- **Workshops:** Content about the partners' participation in workshops, including joint activities with associations will be produced.
- **Training/ Webinars:** A series of training webinars will be produced, giving rise to content production and updates.

The planned dissemination and communication activities will help the project build its community and wider ecosystem, which will boost the project's exploitation and impact creation goals. In this direction, the project will keep track of the XR5.0 community.